

Comparison of outcomes through EPANET and LOOP softwares using a gravity flow water supply network at East Medinipur in West Bengal

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Abstract : Presently drinkable water supply to the residents of any rural area is met mostly from the ground-water sources. Many of the tubewells become dry during summer causing serious water crisis. The Public Health Engineering Directorate under Govt. of West Bengal decided to execute a scheme for withdrawing and delivering surface water from river Rupnarayan to supply drinkable water to the residents of Brindaban-chak Gram Panchayat at Panskura-II block of East Medinipur district in West Bengal. In this study one of a command area zone of close piped network from the above mentioned scheme has been chosen. During the analysis, EPANET software was used. The entire network system consists about 364 numbers of pipes and 337 numbers of junctions. The results were also compared with the outcomes from a popular pipeline designing software LOOP. The obtained flow using EPANET and LOOP softwares had a similarity of around 96%. It suggests that by using either EPANET software or LOOP software the results could be adjusted for pipeline design purpose in future.

Keywords : Simulation, flow control valves, losses in pipelines, accuracy.

I. Introduction

Scarcity of drinking water is the major problem to this modern world. Technologies are growing in leaps and bounds but the supply of the pure drinkable water remains the cause of concern. Historically, cities have been a driving force in the economic and social development of a nation. In India, the cities contribute more than half of country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and also provide more than 60 percent of the country's employment potential. In numerical terms, India's urban population is second largest in the world after China, and is higher than the total urban population of all countries put together barring China, USA and Russia. Such a rapid growth has been possible by migration of population to urban places. Growth of cities involves two processes : enlargement of urban centres and emergence of new towns. Both have played a significant role in growth of urban population and urbanization. But at

the same time it should also be noted that about 70% of India's populations still remain in villages. Though these rural areas get supports from the nearby urban areas, but truly speaking that is not enough for the development of the rural areas in overall perspective. Today maximum of the rural areas lack the consumption of the potable drinking water, they still rely on ponds and other untreated surface or ground water sources. This unhygienic condition leads to an epidemic various times as reported in the news papers and other studies. While coming to the scenario of West Bengal presently potable water to the residents of the rural area is met mostly from groundwater. The groundwater drawn and supplied either by groundwater based Piped Water Supply Scheme with big dia. Tube Wells or small diameter hand pump fitted rig bored tube Wells (spot source). Many of these tube wells become dry during summer causing serious water crisis. Again various types of diseases

also occur due to arsenic and other harmful minerals contaminated in the drinking water. Therefore, it has been decided by PHE Department, Govt. of West Bengal, to execute a Surface Water based Water Supply Scheme for the area by drawing raw water of River Rupnarayan and supplying the same after proper treatment. This will not only provide sustainability in the supply of potable water but also ensure safe and adequate drinking water to the people of command area of the scheme on long term basis.

A pipe network was modeled for a water treatment plant at Dakshin Roypur based on EPANET^{1,2}. It was found that in this network, the time requirement taken for filling different overhead reservoir fully are not similar at all. A computer simulation was made by using EPANET software and obtained the results on the Hanoi water distribution network which was a proper evaluation of the network under normal and abnormal conditions³. A discussion was made about calibration of a model of an operational water distribution system containing pipes of different age⁴ examined. A study was conducted on water demand analysis of Public Water Supply in Municipalities using EPANET software with the aim of providing effective planning, development and operation of water supply and distribution networks which is one of the most essential components of urban infrastructure⁵. Later researchers discussed about reliability based optimal design of water distribution network for municipal water supply using EPANET⁶. Some researchers discussed about correction of the EPANET inaccuracy in computing the efficiency of variable speed pumps⁷.

A study was conducted about a pipe network design and analysis for Dhapa Water Treatment Plant^{8,9}. A comparative study was also carried out about the hydraulic analysis outputs of pipeline network between EPANET and HAMMER softwares for the same plant⁹. The loss of water in pipelines can be a foundation for pressure transiency and can create stress on the piping system. These all are revealed

by using various pipeline hydraulic analysis softwares like EPANET and HAMMER¹⁰. Pipeline alignment will also cause land use change and could be detected by various satellite mapping tools¹¹. The comparative study was carried out with the help of statistical regression analysis by finding out correlation coefficient and probable error coefficient. Later the flow capacity of the pipeline networks were increased in the order of 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% more than the existing flow capacity of the above networks and the transient analyses were done accordingly¹². Increasing trends of hammer head, pressure and circumferential stress with respect to increased flow demand were observed for all the zones which satisfy with wide validation with basic equation for water hammer theoretically. It was also checked whether the pipes are safe for taking the load of increased flow demand. Low flow rates of fixtures were incorporated, the reduced probability of a modern fixture being on at any moment, and reduced confidence level in the binomial probability function as used by Hunter¹³.

Researchers worked on applications where demand on a water supply system changes frequently and widely, the operating conditions of pumps always deviate from the design conditions, and this error leads to poor efficiency and reliability. The developed optimization model provided balance between efficiency and reliability by offering the suitable operating mode¹⁴. Later it was found out if measuring steps can be taken in the water distribution systems then the flow received at many outlets can be very high. Later transient analysis of the pipeline was conducted to study the transient behavior of the proposed raw water pipeline for drinking purpose¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

A discussion was made about open and closed loop pressure control for leakage reduction of pipes. That paper formulated and investigated methods for planning and implementation of online control strategies of predictive and feedback control for areas with many pressures reducing valves and many tar-

get points. The results were applied to an area with three pressure reducing valves and two target points¹⁹.

The command area of the water supply consisted of all Gram Panchayats (GPs) of Panskura-II block of Amalhanda GP, Baishnabchak GP, Bhogpur GP, Brindabanchak GP, Deriachak GP, Gopalnagar GP, Khanyadihi GP, Kola-I and II GP, Pulsita GP, Sagarbarh GP, Siddha-I and II GP considering Geographical features of the area. Total area of the scheme is 143.43 sq. km. Here in this study Brindabanchak GP was considered i.e. the treated water from River Rupnarayan is supplied to the respective overhead reservoir of various GPs in which Brindabanchak GP is one of them.

The drinking water supply scheme implementation objective is to improve rural water supply and sanitation services through progressive decentralization, community participation and enhanced accountability. The objective of the PHED, Panskura-II block is also to augment the capacity of the water supply arrangement of Panskura-II block so as to bridge the existing gap between demand and supply and to adequately meet the projected need of the area to be covered till the year 2043. The proposed scheme will have provision for supply of water through house connection besides a few street hydrants for the benefit of the low income groups.

The study was concentrated (i) to develop a model of pipe network of Zone IV of Panskura Block II under PHED water supply scheme based on EPANET software, (ii) to determine the head losses and flows in pipes alongwith hydraulic grades and pressure at nodes in modeled system, and (iii) to compare the EPANET outcome with LOOP software which is also a simulation software for pipeline analysis.

II. Methodology and assumptions

EPANET software models a water distribution system as a collection of links connected to nodes. The links represent pipes, pumps, and control valves. The nodes represent junctions, tanks and reservoirs.

LOOP software is a part of a package of three microcomputer programs and user instructions prepared by Asia Water Supply and Sanitation Sector Development Team (SDT) for computer-aided planning and design of low-cost water supply and wastewater disposal systems in developing countries.

To study the detail about pipeline network system, following methodology was adopted. The layout map for the whole pipeline network in relation to Panskura water supply system was studied and drawn. The whole network comprising of mainly three routes was considered for analysis as a single system. Before modeling the whole network, live data collection were processed. The layout diagrams of zone IV were collected from Project Management Unit, PHED. The scheduled operation data of the water supply system were noted. According to best available data analysis of distribution network and for getting data was provided by PHED.

The available layout map of the distribution network was modeled into the software named EPANET (Version 2.0) and LOOP (Version 4.0) softwares. Accordingly the whole network was drawn which includes whole serve area.

In the whole layout the hydraulic modeling was carried out in the following process. The reservoir was drawn first, the connecting links such as pipes were drawn the reservoir and the consumer points (junctions) from the toolbar beside software's drawing window. By selecting the pipes, the values of length, diameter and pipe roughness coefficients were entered. Then after modeling the whole network the network analysis run was done and the outputs such as pressure, hydraulic grade line in junctions and unit head loss, velocity, flow in pipes were saved. The total network is basically a mixture of closed and tree type network. Here the closed looped network is been followed when the water of the overhead reservoir is distributed all over the zone. It is also noted that such type of closed loops are followed in the pipes of comparative higher diameters

Fig. 1. Proposed rising main for Panskura-II Block Water Supply (W-S) Scheme (Source : PHED, Govt. of West Bengal).

than the pipe diameters that are coming to consumer end which is notably a tree type network. Since the pressure in main pipes or higher diameter pipes are high and if any one of the looped pipe is broken then the other one can function. Hence a water security at the consumer end and the whole network can be affirmed in case there a breakage in the network. Tree

network means when the pipeline are branched from one node or pipe to different nodes and there is no return back or water from any other path. This type of network can only possible in the extreme end and in case of disturbance in such pipeline only the specific consumer points will be needed to be repaired. So the mixture of tree and closed loop networks are

Das *et al.* : Comparison of outcomes through EPANET and LOOP softwares using a gravity *etc.*

both economically and physically feasible in the rural water distribution.

For running the analysis in the software, few assumptions were made. The water under consideration was supposed to be homogeneous. Elasticity of the water and pipeline material was considered to follow a linear pattern. The flow was one dimensional and the water was incompressible. Average velocity was used for the software analysis. Due to unavailability of valves data at the distribution end, the system was modeled fresh without valves. Water quality simulation was beyond the scope of this present study.

The layout plan of the Zone-IV (Brindabanchak GP) under the distribution system was prepared after extensive survey of the command area and care was taken to cover all roads, lanes, by lanes and foot tracks having habitation alongside. Total demand was 2604 kilo liters per day to supply for eight hours per day. Staging height of the overhead reservoirs was 20 m. Losses due to bend and specials were considered 2 m. All the elevation differences were also taken in consideration. Total head at the entry point of distribution network was 18 m. The length average method was followed to calculate individual nodal demand.

Fig. 2. Satellite view of Chatinda Raw Water Intake Side, East Medinipur, West Bengal.

Hazen William's coefficient (C) for pipe materials was taken as 145 for UPVC (Class-III) pipe and 140 for D.I. (ductile iron) pipe. Minimum outer diameter of pipe was 90 mm. Minimum 7.0 m terminal pressure was maintained throughout the network. The reservoir head and inflow were 23.64 m and 90.46 lps, where the ground elevation of the reservoir is 5.64 m.

In designing the present network the following points have been taken into account. After careful consideration of the nature of soil, accessibility etc., UPVC pipes of Class-III and DI-K7 pipes were used as shown in the drawing. After due consideration of the length and layout of the distribution system and use of UPVC (Class-III) and DI-K7 pipes having high 'C' value of 145 and 140 respectively, the losses in bends and specials have been taken to be 2.0 m. It is to be noted that since the stage height or the overhead reservoir height is 20 m for analysis purpose the total reservoir head is considered to be the addition of the 18 m with the ground elevation of the reservoir which is coming out to be 23.64 m. In view of topography of the area and elevation differences were duly considered in the design.

III. Results and discussion

The inputs of the pipelines were given in accordance with Figs. 3–5. The above figures depict that about 364 pipes or links and 337 nodes or junctions are there in the network. Since the entire network is a giant one so visualization of the flow of water in the whole circular main loop of the pipeline may become very much helpful in pipeline analysis. The results of all the parameters like pressure, hydraulic grade, flow, velocity and unit headloss were found. For a discreet visualization of the network the whole network had been visualized into three routes namely route I, II and III. This bifurcation had been made only to view the total network clearly rest all the calculation and find outs are found by simulating the model of the whole network. The LOOP software becomes very important in selection of the diameters

of the pipes. Proper selection of diameters will help to maintain the system pressure to minimum of 7 m. Results in from the analysis in EPANET software shows that the pressure in each node was maintained at least 7 m. So, for achieving this pressure head upto consumer end point the total reservoir head considered becomes important. Henceforth the reservoir head of 23.64 m holds perfect to guarantee water loss within 15% since twenty meter stage height of the reservoir copes up with total major and minor losses like frictional and fittings losses respectively in the pipeline system. Alongwith here in this networks 2 m loss is about 10% loss with respect to the stage height of the reservoir 20 m as considered for construction. The results from both the softwares mentioned in the study depicts that the velocity didn't exceed 1 m/s. The total pipe length of three routes has been found to be 67.065 km so frictional loss to be assessed to be 2 m. There are many ups and down terrain in the network of 67.065 km. With the help of Figs. 3–5 the air valve locations in order to exhaust the trapped air in uneven terrain of the network where chosen. From Table 1 the locations of

Table 1. Air valve locations

Sl. No.	Air valve locations with respect to Node ID
1.	13
2.	60
3.	73
4.	77
5.	96
6.	125
7.	161
8.	168
9.	179
10.	198
11.	260
12.	283
13.	295
14.	297
15.	315
16.	318

Fig. 3. Pipeline network route-I.

Fig. 4. Pipeline network route-II.

Fig. 5 Pipeline network route-III.

the air valves can be accessed and those nodes can be referred from Figs. 3–5.

From Figs. 6–7 with reference to outcomes as obtained from EPANET, it can be said that the percentage of various hydraulic grades or pressures could

be justified for the whole network as such that both the parameters decrease with the increase in the length of pipelines along with the increase in difference of elevations of the nodes.

The results suggest that maximum conveying

Fig. 6. Frequency plot for distribution of hydraulic grade at nodes over the whole network.

Fig. 7. Frequency plot for distribution of pressure at nodes over the whole network.

length of the pipeline constitute to the main transmission line of the network where the diameters would not be less than 150 mm but also not more than this figure. 90 mm diameter pipes are mainly used at the end links which connects the end nodes which are also termed as the point where the consumer taps the water via 25 mm pipes. The distribution of pressure and hydraulic head also suggest about the population in those terminal nodes. It is obvious that wherever the population is high the pressure or hydraulic grades are also maintained accordingly by alteration of the diameters of the pipes connected to the terminal nodes.

From Figs. 8–10 with reference to the input provided to the softwares, it can be said that percentages of links are more where there is increase of velocity, flow and increase of the unit headless. It is justified on the basis of the geographical locations of the pipelines. Frictional losses are to be avoided here to decrease the unit headloss and that could be done with the help of increase of diameters of pipes at certain locations in the main transmission line. From the inputs it is seen that maximum inter nodal distance is 478 m, and on an average the inter nodal distance is 184 m since this figure is comparatively very much low from the total distance it can be said

that maximum pipes will have desired flow and velocity for fulfilling their nodal requirements and the less number pipes will have a unit headlosses more than 2 m/km since maximum of unit headloss is seen to be in the range 0–1 m/km. So it can be assessed that no problems would exist in respect to the fulfillment of flow requirement at the consumer end. Again this was plausible by the help of choosing appropriate diameter for the pipelines. From the above results Figs. 6–7 and Figs. 8–10 the diameter selection becomes the main parameter since the results are

Fig. 9. Frequency plot for distribution of flow at links over the whole network.

Fig. 8. Frequency plot for distribution of velocity at links over the whole network.

Fig. 10. Frequency plot for distribution of Unit Headloss at links over the whole network.

interlinked with it. The results would be more appropriate if the valve locations are also found out or assessed, this would be very much interesting to see how such parameters respond when the valves are introduced.

From Fig. 11, the main comparison had been made with the outcome of the results of EPANET and LOOP softwares. From the outcomes as seen in Fig. 11, it is justified that the outflow computed in EPANET is varying within $\pm 10\%$ based on overall 96% values in the whole network.

Fig. 11. Comparison for distribution of flow at links over the whole network between results obtained by EPANET and LOOP softwares.

The above result helps in better analyzing the fact that the results of the two softwares could be interchanged with each other and presented where they are compatible. The small change that exists between the outcomes is due the difference in algorithm of the two softwares. Moreover the usage of Modified Hazen Williams method for finding frictional headloss in pipes, in case of algorithm in the LOOP software may diminish the difference in the results of the other software named EPANET.

The Modified Hazen Williams formula is derived

from Darcy Weisbach formula and is as given in eq. (1).

$$V = \frac{3.83 C_r d^{0.6575} (gs)^{0.5525}}{v^{0.105}} \quad (1)$$

where, V is the velocity of flow, C_r is the coefficient of roughness, d is the pipe diameter, g is the acceleration due to gravity, s is the hydraulic gradient and v is the viscosity of fluid. The modified Hazen Williams method is also applicable to the low flow criterion in pipes so LOOP cannot assess those values in the pipes where the flow is comparatively very low. But at the same the EPANET software cannot find out the diameters by its own. So suggestion to the engineers would be to take the help from LOOP software to find the diameters of the pipes then analyze the same in EPANET and make few changes in diameter to get the accuracy in results.

IV. Conclusion

The present study is dealt with the analysis of the drinking water pipeline distribution network of Brindabanchak GP, Panskura Block II under PHED of West Bengal. By observing the results of the pressures and hydraulic grade of the total system along with few undulations due geography as depicted in several tables of elevations, it can be pointed out that the usage of air valves are much very important to address this issue. The whole network of service area under PHED consists about 364 pipes and 363 junctions. Moreover the junctions here act as the network outlet also. Hence detailed outcomes in graphical and tabular format were represented in graphical form as per as possible. Thereby the system flow found out in EPANET can be adjusted with LOOP software to achieve around 96% accuracy. The input data provided in this study is mostly on the basis of the experience in other pipeline networks along with the original survey done in Panskura

Block II. These parameters may or may not match original field data since the whole network discussed here is in proposal stage. The piped network had also been compared with an optimized piping network simulating software named LOOP. It must be general practice not to design the pipeline by relying in any one of the software, since each of these softwares have its own limitations. In this study the advantages and disadvantages of both the software had been put forward. A good design could only be possible if all the advantages of the softwares could be clubbed together. Likewise initially by viewing the survey drawing, an optimized design is to be done in LOOP where the information of optimized pipe diameter could be found. Since it is a pressure pipeline – the whole system is to be modelled in EPANET software as here the elements of the pipelines could be viewed in same platform alongwith the other hydraulic parameters. LOOP software is old in respect to EPANET software so developments in the field of hydraulics might not be incorporated in it. But the software cannot be thrown away because of its specialty to find out optimum diameter for each pipe in the pipeline. This study is hoped to open up possibilities of usage of various types of fittings and management techniques in order to provide undisturbed water supply at its required demand. Since the whole network analysis is based on direct pipe flow so a many flow outcome may differ a commandable amount in reality so proper usage of valves are required.

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